

Dual-energy computed tomography (CT) versus cone-beam computed tomography (CT) in chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension: diagnostic accuracy compared with digital subtraction angiography

A. Páez-Carpio^{a,b,c,d,*,†}, E. Serrano^e, B. Domenech-Ximenes^b,
L. Cornellàs^f, J.A. Barberà^{c,d,g,h}, I. Vollmer^{f,#}, I. Blanco^{c,d,g,h,#},
F.M. Gómez^{i,#}

^a Department of Medical Imaging, University of Toronto, Toronto, M5T1W7, ON, Canada

^b Department of Radiology, CDI, Hospital Clínic Barcelona, Barcelona, 08036, Spain

^c Institut d'Investigacions Biomèdiques August Pi i Sunyer (IDIBAPS), Barcelona, 08036, Spain

^d Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, Universitat de Barcelona, Barcelona, 08036, Spain

^e Department of Radiology, Hospital Universitari de Bellvitge, L'Hospitalet de Llobregat, 08907, Spain

^f Department of Radiology, Hospital Universitari Vall d'Hebron, Barcelona, 08035, Spain

^g Biomedical Research Networking Centre on Respiratory Diseases (CIBERES), Madrid, Spain

^h Department of Pulmonary Medicine, ICR, Hospital Clínic Barcelona, Barcelona, 08036, Spain

ⁱ Department of Radiology, Hospital Universitari i Politècnic La Fe, València, 46026, Spain

ARTICLE INFORMATION

Article history:

Received 6 August 2025

Received in revised form

30 September 2025

Accepted 27 October 2025

AIM: The aim of this study was to compare the diagnostic accuracy and interobserver agreement of dual-energy computed tomography pulmonary angiography (DECT-PA) and cone-beam computed tomography pulmonary angiography (CBCT-PA) for the evaluation of chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension (CTEPH), using digital subtraction angiography pulmonary angiography (DSA-PA) as the reference standard.

MATERIALS AND METHODS: This retrospective study included 109 patients with confirmed CTEPH who underwent DECT-PA, CBCT-PA, and DSA-PA within a three-month interval between January 2017 and June 2022. Pulmonary arteries were evaluated at main, lobar, segmental, and subsegmental levels. Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV),

Abbreviations: BPA, Balloon pulmonary angioplasty; CBCT-PA, Cone-Beam CT pulmonary angiography; CTEPH, Chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension; CTPA, CT pulmonary angiography; DECT-PA, Dual-energy CT pulmonary angiography; DSA-PA, Digital subtraction pulmonary angiography; mPAP, Mean pulmonary arterial pressure; NPV, Negative predictive value; NYHA-FC, New York Heart Association Functional Class; PEA, Pulmonary endarterectomy; PPV, Positive predictive value; PVR, Pulmonary vascular resistance; V/Q, Ventilation–perfusion scintigraphy; WU, Wood units.

* Guarantor and correspondent: Alfredo Páez-Carpio, MD, PhD, EDIR, EBIR, Department of Medical Imaging, University of Toronto, Toronto, M5T1W7, ON, Canada.

E-mail address: alfredo.paezcarpio@mail.utoronto.ca (A. Páez-Carpio).

✉ (A. Páez-Carpio)

These authors collaborated equally as co-senior authors.

† Present/permanent address: 263 McCaul St 4th floor, Toronto, ON M5T 1W7.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crad.2025.107152>

0009-9260/© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Ltd on behalf of The Royal College of Radiologists. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

negative predictive value (NPV), and diagnostic accuracy were calculated. Interobserver agreement was assessed using Cohen's kappa (κ).

RESULTS: Overall diagnostic accuracy was comparable between DECT-PA (89.5%) and CBCT-PA (89.3%). DECT-PA demonstrated higher overall sensitivity (65.0% vs 53.5%, $P = 0.019$) but CBCT-PA achieved greater interobserver agreement ($\kappa = 0.76$ vs 0.74). Sensitivity declined in distal segments for both modalities, with CBCT-PA outperforming DECT-PA at the subsegmental level (51.9% vs 43.6%). Specificity remained high across modalities (>89%). The CBCT-PA showed superior agreement for lesion subtype classification, particularly for occlusions ($\kappa = 0.839$).

CONCLUSION: DECT-PA and CBCT-PA offer complementary strengths for the evaluation of CTEPH. DECT-PA provides high specificity for central and segmental lesions, supporting its role in initial assessment. CBCT-PA improves sensitivity and reproducibility in distal arteries, reinforcing its value for procedural planning and detailed vascular assessment. These findings support the use of DECT-PA as a first-line diagnostic tool and highlight the role of CBCT-PA as an adjunct in patients with distal or morphologically complex disease, potentially influencing diagnostic pathways and procedural planning in CTEPH.

© 2025 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Ltd on behalf of The Royal College of Radiologists. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

Chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension (CTEPH) is a rare (3–5/100,000) and potentially fatal condition classified within group 4 pulmonary hypertension, defined by persistent pulmonary arterial obstruction with a mean pulmonary arterial pressure (mPAP) > 20 mmHg and pulmonary vascular resistance (PVR) > 2 Wood units (WU), despite >3 months of effective anticoagulation.^{1–5} Although potentially curable, CTEPH diagnosis remains challenging due to nonspecific symptoms and heterogeneous imaging findings.^{6,7} Following initial screening with ventilation–perfusion (V/Q) scintigraphy, precise anatomical imaging is essential to localise and characterise obstructive lesions, thereby guiding appropriate therapy.^{8–10}

Computed tomography pulmonary angiography (CTPA) is widely used but has limited accuracy at distal levels, where lesion detection critically informs patient eligibility for pulmonary endarterectomy (PEA) or balloon pulmonary angioplasty (BPA).^{8,9,11} Current guidelines prioritise V/Q scintigraphy and CTPA for initial evaluation, yet significant uncertainty persists in the assessment of distal disease.^{8–10} Reported segmental sensitivities range from 67% to 74%, with further declines at the subsegmental level. Dual-energy computed tomography pulmonary angiography (DECT-PA) has reported sensitivities up to 94%, although its diagnostic performance varies across arterial levels and may be influenced by lesion morphology and reader expertise.^{9,10,12} Cone-beam computed tomography pulmonary angiography (CBCT-PA), acquired during digital subtraction angiography pulmonary angiography (DSA-PA), offers high spatial resolution and has demonstrated potential for detecting distal thromboembolic lesions.¹³ Although CBCT-PA is invasive, its ability to depict subtle distal targets could be transformative for BPA planning. In

comparative studies, CBCT-PA may identify and characterise more abnormalities than DSA and CTPA at segmental and subsegmental levels.^{14–16}

To date, no study has directly compared the diagnostic value of DECT-PA and CBCT-PA using DSA-PA as the reference standard. This comparison is clinically relevant as accurate detection of distal thromboembolic lesions directly influences treatment planning and patient outcomes. Therefore, the aim of this study was to compare the diagnostic accuracy of DECT-PA and CBCT-PA in detecting chronic thromboembolic lesions at main, lobar, segmental, and subsegmental levels, using DSA-PA as the reference standard. To our knowledge, this is the first study to directly compare the diagnostic performance and interobserver reproducibility of DECT-PA and CBCT-PA across all pulmonary arterial levels, using DSA-PA as the reference standard.

Material and methods

Study design

This retrospective single-centre study was conducted at a tertiary academic institution with a dedicated multidisciplinary CTEPH unit. Institutional review board approval was obtained, and informed consent was waived. Patients with CTEPH evaluated between January 2017 and June 2022 were retrospectively identified. Inclusion criteria were patients aged ≥ 18 years who underwent DECT-PA, CBCT-PA, and DSA-PA within a maximum interval of 3 months as part of their CTEPH work-up. Patients were excluded if any imaging interval exceeded 3 months, if DECT-PA was performed using single-energy acquisition, if CBCT-PA was not acquired during the DSA-PA session, or if the patient had previously undergone PEA or BPA treatment.

Imaging protocols

The DECT-PA was performed using a dual-source CT system (SOMATOM Definition Flash®, Siemens Healthineers®, Erlangen, Germany). Acquisition parameters included 80 kV and 140 kV tube voltages, 100–300 mAs, pitch 0.6, and a rotation time of 0.25 seconds. Bolus tracking was used with 75–85 mL of iodine-based contrast medium (Ultravist® 370, Bayer, Leverkusen, Germany), followed by a 30 mL saline flush at 5 mL/s. Contrast was administered using antecubital fossa venous access with a 20G cannula. Images were reconstructed using ADMIRE® (Siemens Healthineers®, Erlangen, Germany) (Level 3) with Br40 (mediastinal) and Br64 (lung) kernels. Transverse series were generated with 1 mm slice thickness for mediastinal, lung, and DECT iodine maps.

The CBCT-PA was performed in a flat-panel angiography suite (ArtisQ®, Siemens Healthineers®, Erlangen, Germany) using an Angled 5Fr pigtail catheter (Performa®, Merit Medical®, South Jordan, UT, USA) placed in the main pulmonary artery via right jugular venous access using a 5 Fr/10 cm vascular sheath (Pinnacle®, Terumo®, Tokyo, Japan). All procedures were performed by one of the board-certified interventional radiologists from our team, with experience ranging from 2 to 20 years. A total of 80 mL of contrast (70 mL iodine-based contrast medium + 10 mL saline) was injected at 8–10 mL/s using a dual-chamber injector. Acquisitions were performed with a 5 sDR DynaCT preset (100–120 kV, 100–300 mA, 5-second rotation, 30 × 40 cm FOV). Reconstructions included transverse, multiplanar, and three-dimensional (3D) reformats.

The DSA-PA was performed immediately following CBCT-PA using the same access and equipment as CBCT-PA. Selective pulmonary angiograms were acquired in standard posteroanterior, lateral (90°), and oblique (45°) projections using an angled 5 Fr pigtail catheter (Performa®, Merit Medical®, South Jordan, UT, USA). Each run involved 20–25 mL of iodine-based contrast medium injected at 10–12 mL/s with a 2-second delay, at six frames/second, 60–80 kV and 200–400 mAs.

Image interpretation

All studies were interpreted independently by two radiologists per modality, blinded to other results. DECT-PA images were reviewed by two board-certified chest radiologists (4 and 7 years of experience), and CBCT-PA and DSA-PA by two board-certified interventional radiologists (5 and 7 years of experience). A washout period of at least one month was observed between CBCT-PA and DSA-PA readings. All imaging evaluations were performed through independent readings by two radiologists per modality, and independent readings were considered final. All images were reviewed using the Syngo.via® software (Siemens Healthineers®, Erlangen, Germany).

Perfusion maps on DECT-PA were qualitatively assessed for hypoperfusion, defined as visibly decreased iodine distribution compared to adjacent segments. For all modalities, pulmonary arterial trees were evaluated bilaterally

at four anatomical levels (main, lobar, segmental, and subsegmental). Lesions were classified as present or absent. If present, they were categorised as occlusion or stenosis. Segmental stenoses were further subclassified as web/band, peripheral thrombotic material, or ring-like stenosis.

Statistical analysis

Descriptive statistics summarised demographic, clinical, and procedural data. Continuous variables were reported as means with standard deviations or medians with interquartile ranges, depending on data distribution. Categorical variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages. Sample size calculations were not conducted due to the retrospective nature of the study, but power analysis was performed post hoc to validate key findings. Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV) were calculated for DECT-PA and CBCT-PA using DSA-PA as the reference standard, stratified by arterial level and lesion type. Overall diagnostic accuracy was assessed for both modalities. Interobserver agreement was evaluated using Cohen's kappa (κ). Paired comparisons between DECT-PA and CBCT-PA were performed with McNemar's test. Generalised linear mixed models and beta-binomial regression accounted for within-patient clustering and multiple arterial levels. This approach was chosen to appropriately model the hierarchical structure of the data, allowing for correlation between multiple arterial segments evaluated within the same patient. Comparisons stratified by arterial level and lesion subtype were considered exploratory and reported descriptively without formal hypothesis testing, to avoid inflation of type I error given the multiplicity of comparisons and within-patient clustering. A two-sided P value <0.05 was considered statistically significant. Statistical analyses were performed using R software (v.2024.12, R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria).

Results

Baseline characteristics

Of the 210 patients assessed, 109 met all inclusion criteria and were included in the analysis. The most common reason for exclusion was an interval >3 months between DECT and CBCT/DSA ($n = 42$) (Fig 1). The cohort included 60 men (53.1%), with a mean age of 60.1 years (standard deviation [SD]: 16.1). The mean interval between DSA/CBCT and DECT was 26.5 days (SD: 28.2). The mean mPAP was 34 mmHg (SD: 14.1), and most patients were grade III in the New York Heart Association (NYHA) functional class (53, 46.9%) (Table 1).

Overall diagnostic performance

In total, 226 main, 678 lobar, and 2,147 segmental pulmonary arteries were evaluated (Figs 2 and 3). Overall diagnostic accuracy was comparable between DECT-PA

Figure 1 Flowchart of patient selection and study design.

Table 1
Baseline patient characteristics.

	N = 109
Age, years	60.8 (16.1)
BMI, kg/m²	28.3 (7.9)
Gender, male	60 (53.1)
Time between DECT-PA and DSA-PA/CBCT-PA, days	26.5 (28.2)
NYHA-FC	
I	4 (3.5)
II	45 (39.8)
III	53 (46.9)
IV	10 (8.8)
BNP	65.9 (237.5)
NT-proBNP	284 (2509.5)
6MWD, metres	420 (129)
mPAP, mmHg	34 (14.1)
PVR, WU	5.1 (4.9)
Cardiac output, L/min	4.3 (1.3)
Cardiac index, L/min/m²	2.3 (0.6)

Categorical variables are expressed in **total values (%)** and continuous variables in **mean (SD)**.

BMI, body mass index; BNP, B-type natriuretic peptide; CBCT-PA, cone-beam CT pulmonary angiography; DECT-PA, dual-energy CT pulmonary angiography; DSAPA, digital subtraction pulmonary angiography; mPAP, mean pulmonary artery pressure; NT-proBNP, N-terminal pro-B-type natriuretic peptide; NYHA-FC, New York Heart Association functional class; PVR, peripheral vascular resistance; 6MWD, 6 minutes walking distance; WU, Wood units.

(89.5%) and CBCT-PA (89.3%) ($P = 0.641$). DECT-PA showed significantly higher sensitivity (65.0%; 95% confidence interval [CI]: 59.0–70.0%) than CBCT-PA (53.5%; 95% CI: 47.0–60.0%; $P = 0.019$). Specificity varied by lesion type: DECT-PA outperformed CBCT-PA for overall vessel involvement ($P = 0.0175$), stenosis ($P = 0.0418$), and subsegmental detection ($P < 0.001$), whereas CBCT-PA demonstrated higher specificity for distinguishing single vs multiple subsegmental lesions ($P < 0.001$) (Fig 4) (Table 2). No significant differences were found in PPV (DECT-PA: 15.5%, CBCT-PA: 14.8%; $P = 0.548$) or NPV (DECT-PA: 98.0%, CBCT-PA: 97.8%; $P = 0.177$).

Performance by arterial levels

At the main artery level, DECT-PA achieved 100% sensitivity and 93.9% specificity. CBCT-PA had lower sensitivity (50.0%) and similar specificity (95.4%). For lobar arteries, DECT-PA showed higher sensitivity (69.9%) and slightly lower specificity (85.3%) than CBCT-PA (62.6% and 88.1%, respectively). For occlusions, DECT-PA and CBCT-PA showed similar sensitivity (61.9% vs 64.3%) and specificity (98.1% vs 98.3%). For stenotic lesions, DECT-PA had higher sensitivity (56.3%) and slightly lower specificity (86.6%)

Figure 2 Multimodal evaluation of thromboembolic lesions. (a) Transverse DECT-PA in a 64-year-old man showing a chronic thrombus in the left main pulmonary artery (thick white arrow). (b) Transverse iodine perfusion map from DECT-PA in a 58-year-old woman demonstrating a perfusion defect in the right lower lobe (white arrow) with additional hypoperfusion in the posterior basal segment (black arrowhead). (c) Coronal CBCT-PA in a 71-year-old man revealing a web-like lesion in the right lower lobar artery (white triangle) and complete occlusions in the anterior basal and medial basal segmental arteries (white arrows). (d) DSA-PA in a 55-year-old woman confirming multiple subsegmental perfusion defects in the right upper and lower lobes (black arrows). CBCT-PA, cone-beam computed tomography pulmonary angiography; DECT-PA, dual-energy computed tomography pulmonary angiography.

Figure 3 Representative examples of chronic thromboembolic lesion subtypes across imaging modalities. (a) CBCT-PA in a 67-year-old man showing occlusions of the right lower lobar artery and the anterior segmental artery of the right upper lobe (white arrows). (b) Transverse DECT-PA in a 59-year-old woman demonstrating a web-like lesion affecting the right lower lobar artery (white arrow). (c) DSA-PA in a 73-year-old man showing a classic ring-like stenosis in the apical segmental artery of the right upper lobe (white arrow). CBCT-PA, cone-beam computed tomography pulmonary angiography; DECT-PA, dual-energy computed tomography pulmonary angiography; DSA-PA, digital subtraction angiography pulmonary angiography.

than CBCT-PA (45.8% and 89.1%). At the segmental level, CBCT-PA showed higher sensitivity (75.6%) than DECT-PA (69.4%), with lower specificity (47.4% vs 60.1%). Sensitivity for occlusions was similar (DECT-PA: 52.3%, CBCT-

PA: 57.6%), with high specificity for both (DECT-PA: 92.8%, CBCT-PA: 92.1%). For stenosis, DECT-PA showed lower sensitivity (44.0%) but higher specificity (73.7%) than CBCT-PA (52.7% and 64.7%, respectively). At the

Figure 4 Comparison of sensitivity and specificity between DECT-PA and CBCT-PA across arterial levels. Sensitivity and specificity are shown for DECT-PA (blue tones) and CBCT-PA (green tones) across main, lobar, segmental, and subsegmental pulmonary arteries. Darker tones represent specificity, and lighter tones represent sensitivity. Bars represent point estimates. CBCT-PA, cone-beam computed tomography pulmonary angiography; DECT-PA, dual-energy computed tomography pulmonary angiography.

subsegmental level, sensitivity was higher for CBCT-PA (51.9%) than DECT-PA (43.6%), while DECT-PA showed higher specificity (72.3% vs 60.0%). CBCT-PA demonstrated significantly better performance in distinguishing single vs multiple subsegmental lesions (specificity: 82.4% vs 71.9%; $P < 0.001$).

Lesion subtypes analysis

For occlusions, sensitivity was 52.3% (95% CI: 46.0–58.4%) for DECT-PA and 57.6% (95% CI: 51.2–63.7%) for CBCT-PA. Interobserver agreement was highest for CBCT-PA ($\kappa = 0.839$), followed by DECT-PA ($\kappa = 0.658$) and DSA-PA ($\kappa = 0.549$). For stenotic lesions, DECT-PA showed

the highest sensitivity for wall-adherent thrombotic material (68.2%; 95% CI: 61.5–74.2%), followed by ring-like stenosis (55.1%; 95% CI: 49.3–60.7%) and webs or bands (49.4%; 95% CI: 43.2–55.7%). CBCT-PA demonstrated the highest sensitivity for webs or bands (63.7%; 95% CI: 57.9–69.2%) and ring-like stenosis (60.5%; 95% CI: 54.8–66.0%), followed by wall-adherent thrombotic material (51.2%; 95% CI: 44.7–57.6%).

Interobserver agreement

Overall interobserver agreement was highest for CBCT-PA ($\kappa = 0.76$), followed by DECT-PA ($\kappa = 0.74$) and DSA-PA ($\kappa = 0.57$) ($p < 0.001$) (Fig 5) (Table 3). Main pulmonary interobserver agreement was excellent for CBCT-PA ($\kappa = 0.82$), DECT-PA ($\kappa = 0.80$), and DSA-PA ($\kappa = 0.81$); differences were not statistically significant ($P = 0.121$). At the lobar level, interobserver agreement was significantly higher for CBCT-PA ($\kappa = 0.77$) than for DECT-PA ($\kappa = 0.75$; $P = 0.030$) and DSA-PA ($\kappa = 0.60$; $P = 0.003$). At the segmental level, interobserver agreement was significantly better for CBCT-PA ($\kappa = 0.70$) than for DECT-PA ($\kappa = 0.68$; $P = 0.015$) and DSA-PA ($\kappa = 0.58$; $P < 0.001$). Interobserver agreement at the subsegmental level was moderate for CBCT-PA ($\kappa = 0.64$), lower for DECT-PA ($\kappa = 0.53$), and lowest for DSA-PA ($\kappa = 0.54$); differences were not statistically significant ($P = 0.102$). Finally, interobserver agreement for stenosis-type classification was also highest for CBCT-PA ($\kappa = 0.679$), followed by DECT-PA ($\kappa = 0.433$) and DSA-PA ($\kappa = 0.275$) (Table 4).

Table 2
Diagnostic performance by modality and arterial level.

	Modality	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	n=2943	
				PPV	NPV
Overall	DECT-PA	65.0	89.5	15.5	98.0
	CBCT-PA	53.5	89.3	14.8	97.8
Main	DECT-PA	100	93.9	7.8	100
	CBCT-PA	50.0	95.4	4.2	99.8
Lobar	DECT-PA	69.9	85.3	39.2	95.4
	CBCT-PA	62.6	88.1	40.5	94.6
Segmental	DECT-PA	69.4	60.1	71.1	57.9
	CBCT-PA	75.6	47.4	67.5	57.6
Subsegmental	DECT-PA	43.6	72.3	51.4	65.4
	CBCT-PA	51.9	60.0	46.7	64.9

CBCT-PA, cone-beam CT pulmonary angiography; DECT-PA, dual-energy CT pulmonary angiography; NPV, negative predictive value; PPV, positive predictive value.

Figure 5 Interobserver agreement by arterial level and imaging modality. DECT-PA (blue), CBCT-PA (red), and DSA-PA (green). Agreement was highest at proximal levels ($\kappa > 0.80$) and declined distally. Substantial to excellent agreement was maintained by DECT-PA and CBCT-PA down to the segmental level, while DSA-PA demonstrated greater variability and lower reproducibility overall. The dashed horizontal line indicates threshold for excellent agreement ($\kappa = 0.75$). CBCT-PA, cone-beam computed tomography pulmonary angiography; DECT-PA, dual-energy computed tomography pulmonary angiography; DSA-PA, digital subtraction angiography pulmonary angiography.

Table 3
Interobserver agreement for lesion detection by modality and arterial level.

	DECT-PA (κ)	CBCT-PA (κ)	DSA-PA (κ)
Overall	0.74	0.76	0.57
By arterial level			
Main branches	0.80	0.82	0.81
Lobar branches	0.75	0.77	0.60
Segmental branches	0.68	0.70	0.58
Subsegmental	0.53	0.64	0.54

κ : Cohen's kappa coefficient. CBCT-PA, cone-beam computed tomography pulmonary angiography; DECT-PA, dual-energy computed tomography pulmonary angiography; DSA-PA, digital subtraction angiography pulmonary angiography.

Cohen's κ values are presented for each modality. Values > 0.75 are shown in **bold** to indicate excellent agreement. Slight: 0.01–0.20; fair: 0.21–0.40; moderate: 0.41–0.60; substantial: 0.61–0.80; almost perfect: >0.81 .

Discussion

This study represents a large cohort comparing DECT-PA and CBCT-PA in the evaluation of CTEPH, encompassing nearly 3,000 pulmonary arterial segments analysed with a standardised interpretation protocol. We evaluated the diagnostic performance of DECT-PA and CBCT-PA for the assessment of CTEPH using DSA-PA as the reference standard in a large cohort. Both modalities demonstrated comparable overall diagnostic accuracy, exceeding 89%. DECT-PA exhibited higher sensitivity across most arterial levels, particularly in central and lobar arteries. However, sensitivity progressively decreased in distal segments, with both modalities showing reduced detection rates at the

Table 4
Diagnostic performance by modality and lesion type.

	Modality	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	κ
Occlusion	DECT-PA	52.3	92.8	0.66
	CBCT-PA	57.6	92.1	0.84
Webs/bands	DECT-PA	49.4	73.7	0.43
	CBCT-PA	63.7	64.7	0.68
Ring-like stenosis	DECT-PA	55.1	73.7	0.43
	CBCT-PA	60.5	64.7	0.68
Wall-adherent thrombus	DECT-PA	68.2	73.7	0.43
	CBCT-PA	51.2	64.7	0.68

CBCT-PA, cone-beam computed tomography pulmonary angiography; DECT-PA, dual-energy computed tomography pulmonary angiography.

subsegmental level. CBCT-PA achieved greater interobserver agreement across all levels, suggesting more consistent performance between readers, especially for segmental and subsegmental arteries.

Compared with previous studies evaluating imaging modalities in CTEPH, our cohort demonstrated lower sensitivity values, particularly at the segmental and subsegmental levels. DECT-PA achieved 69.4% sensitivity at the segmental level and 43.6% at the subsegmental level, while CBCT-PA achieved 75.6% and 51.9%, respectively. Beyond angiographic depiction, DECT-PA provides iodine maps that can highlight perfusion defects and increase diagnostic confidence, particularly in central and lobar disease. However, our findings confirm that its value is more limited in isolated distal disease, where sensitivity declines markedly. Moreover, these rates are lower than those

reported for V/Q single-photon emission computed tomography (SPECT) imaging, where segmental sensitivity typically exceeds 90%, and also fall below the performance of CTPA described in recent systematic reviews.^{6,9,10,12,17} However, methodological differences must be emphasised. Our study used DSA-PA as the sole gold standard, applying stricter criteria and penalising minor discordances that consensus-based approaches or composite standards might absorb. Furthermore, interpretations were performed independently without consensus arbitration, better simulating real-world practice but potentially lowering measured sensitivity. Our systematic evaluation of distal arteries increased detection challenges compared with studies focused on central disease.¹⁸ Despite these challenges, both DECT-PA and CBCT-PA achieved high overall diagnostic accuracy (89.5% and 89.3%, respectively), supported by consistently high specificity (>89%) and very high NPVs (>97%). These findings align with early reports using 64-slice CT showing excellent segmental-level sensitivity and specificity but highlight the increasing diagnostic difficulty as lesion burden shifts distally.¹⁹ Moreover, although DECT-PA parameters have been shown to differentiate CTEPH from chronic thromboembolic disease with reasonable accuracy, their performance in isolated distal disease remains limited, especially in more distal arteries.^{17,20–22} Notably, while V/Q SPECT prioritises sensitivity, this often comes at the cost of lower specificity and more false-positive interpretations.^{9,12} In contrast, the specificity observed in our study compares favourably with DECT perfusion and hybrid protocols and supports the reliability of DECT-PA and CBCT-PA for ruling out haemodynamically significant disease.^{13,17,23–26} Beyond cross-sectional imaging, CBCT-PA has been shown to outperform CT and DSA for identifying subtle distal lesions such as webs, bands, and ring-like stenoses.^{13–16} These findings are consistent with our observation of enhanced sensitivity and reproducibility for CBCT-PA in distal vessels. However, they emphasise the necessity of standardised acquisition and interpretation protocols to maximise diagnostic consistency.

CBCT-PA demonstrated the highest reproducibility across all arterial levels, achieving a κ value of 0.76 overall, and maintaining substantial to excellent agreement even at the segmental ($\kappa = 0.70$) and subsegmental ($\kappa = 0.64$) levels. DECT-PA also achieved substantial agreement overall ($\kappa = 0.74$) but showed a more pronounced decline in distal branches ($\kappa = 0.53$ at the subsegmental level). These findings are consistent with prior observations emphasising the limitations of conventional and DECT techniques for detecting subtle distal lesions, where diagnostic confidence and inter-reader consistency often decrease.^{10,18,20,27} Similarly to our findings, Hinrichs et al. previously demonstrated superior intermodality agreement for CBCT-PA ($\kappa = 0.96$) compared with DSA ($\kappa = 0.61$), supporting the utility of CBCT-PA for procedural guidance and comprehensive assessment of vascular abnormalities.¹⁶ Although DECT-PA offers the advantage of broader availability and noninvasive acquisition, its reproducibility may be inherently limited by lower spatial resolution and

greater reliance on perfusion artefacts for lesion characterisation.^{10,20} Together, these findings suggest that CBCT-PA not only improves sensitivity in distal vessels but also offers a reproducibility profile superior to that of traditional cross-sectional techniques, mainly for lesions with complex or subtle morphologies.

The combined findings of diagnostic performance and interobserver agreement in our study may have direct implications for clinical practice. DECT-PA, with its increasing availability, noninvasive nature, and rapid acquisition, remains a practical first-line modality for the diagnostic evaluation and longitudinal follow-up of patients with CTEPH. Its high specificity and NPV support its use for ruling out clinically significant obstruction. However, the loss of diagnostic consistency and sensitivity in more distal branches demonstrated in our study exposes the inherent limitations in accurately detecting small or morphologically subtle lesions. In contrast, CBCT-PA, despite its invasive nature and requirement for specialised equipment and expertise, offers superior reproducibility and enhanced visualisation of complex distal lesions, especially during BPA planning. In the context of newly established BPA programmes, where operator experience may initially be limited, imaging techniques that improve lesion detection consistency are critical to minimising procedural risks. CBCT-PA not only enhances sensitivity for distal lesions but also improves morphological characterisation, allowing safer and more confident lesion targeting compared to reliance on DSA-PA alone.²⁸ The identification of subtle subsegmental lesions has direct therapeutic implications as these sites may be potential targets for BPA. While isolated findings may not always alter immediate treatment, their recognition improves procedural planning by preventing underestimation of disease burden and reducing the risk of incomplete revascularisation. These observations suggest that integrating CBCT-PA into procedural workflows may help flatten the learning curve and enhance both safety and efficacy in centres initiating BPA programmes. Finally, from a diagnostic pathway perspective, DECT-PA remains preferable as a noninvasive first-line test, providing rapid anatomical and perfusion information and strong NPV. CBCT-PA, although invasive, offers superior consistency in distal disease and may be most useful for BPA planning in patients with inconclusive or distal-only lesions. Compared with V/Q SPECT, DECT-PA and CBCT-PA achieve higher specificity, while SPECT retains the advantage of greater sensitivity.

Several limitations should be acknowledged. First, its retrospective design and single-centre nature may limit the generalisability of the findings. Additionally, the absence of a CTED control group precluded direct comparison with patients without pulmonary hypertension, which may have limited the scope of our findings. Although imaging interpretations were performed independently by experienced readers, no consensus arbitration was performed to resolve discrepancies, potentially amplifying inter-reader variability compared to consensus-based series. Second, while DSA-PA was used as the reference standard, its limitations, particularly in detecting distal lesions obscured by

vessel overlap or limited contrast opacification, may have contributed to the apparent underestimation of sensitivity. Nevertheless, DSA was selected in line with current international guidelines, which continue to recognise it as the gold standard for the diagnostic evaluation of CTEPH, despite these limitations. Third, the classification of vascular lesions was simplified into binary occlusion vs stenosis categories for vessel-based analysis, although further granularity was explored through lesion subtype evaluation. Fourth, DECT-PA and CBCT-PA were not performed simultaneously; despite restricting inclusion to studies performed within a three-month interval, temporal progression of disease or treatment effects cannot be entirely excluded. Moreover, formal radiation dose comparison between DECT-PA and CBCT-PA was not performed, as this was outside the scope of the present analysis. Furthermore, the impact of lesion subtype identification on clinical decision-making and procedural outcomes was not assessed, highlighting the need for future prospective studies to validate the prognostic relevance of imaging-based lesion characterisation. In addition, differences in equipment vendors, acquisition protocols, and institutional experience may influence diagnostic performance, which could limit generalisability across centres.

Conclusion

DECT-PA and CBCT-PA offer complementary strengths in the diagnostic evaluation of CTEPH. DECT-PA provides high specificity and NPV for central and segmental lesions, supporting its role in initial screening. CBCT-PA enhances sensitivity and reproducibility in distal arteries and complex morphological lesions, reinforcing its value for procedural planning and detailed vascular assessment.

Author contribution

1. Guarantor of integrity of the entire study: Alfredo Páez-Carpio.

2. Study concepts and design: Alfredo Páez-Carpio, Isabel Blanco, Fernando M. Gómez, and Ivan Vollmer.

3. Literature research: Alfredo Páez-Carpio.

4. Clinical studies: Alfredo Páez-Carpio, Blanca Domenech-Ximenes, Elena Serrano, Lúria Cornellias, and Isabel Blanco.

5. Experimental studies/data analysis: Alfredo Páez-Carpio and Isabel Blanco.

6. Statistical analysis: Alfredo Páez-Carpio (basic); external statistical provider (complex).

7. Manuscript preparation: Alfredo Páez-Carpio.

8. Manuscript editing: Alfredo Páez-Carpio, Isabel Blanco, Ivan Vollmer, Elena Serrano, Joan A. Barberà, Fernando M. Gómez, and Blanca Domenech-Ximenes.

Data availability

The dataset used for this study is not publicly available as institutional consent for data sharing was not obtained

from Hospital Clínic Barcelona. However, data may be made available by the corresponding author upon reasonable request and subject to institutional approval.

Ethics

This study was approved by the Research Ethics Board (CEIM) of Hospital Clínic Barcelona, Spain (HCB/2021/0054), and the requirement for informed consent was waived. All procedures performed followed the ethical standards of the institutional and/or national research committee and with the 1964 Helsinki Declaration and its later amendments or comparable ethical standards.

Funding

This study was funded by the Sociedad Española de Radiología Médica (SERAM). Grant: 2021 - 04_FGM_INVESTIGACION_SERAM_2021.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Acknowledgements

In loving memory of Alejandro Páez-Carpio, MD. XpertScientific Editing and Consulting Services assisted with statistical analysis.

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

References

- Humbert M, Kovacs G, Hoeper MM, et al. ESC/ERS guidelines for the diagnosis and treatment of pulmonary hypertension. *Eur Respir J* 2023;**61**:2200879, <https://doi.org/10.1183/13993003.00879-2022>.
- Escribano Subias P, Blanco I, López Meseguer M, et al. Survival in pulmonary hypertension in Spain: insights from the Spanish registry. *Eur Respir J* 2012;**40**:596–603. <https://doi.org/10.1183/09031936.00101211>.
- Delcroix M, Torbicki A, Gopalan D, et al. ERS statement on chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension. *Eur Respir J* 2021;**57**:2002828, <https://doi.org/10.1183/13993003.02828-2021>.
- De Perrot M, Gopalan D, Jenkins D, et al. Evaluation and management of patients with chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension – consensus statement from the ISHLT. *J Heart Lung Transplant* 2021;**40**:1301–26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healun.2021.05.012>.
- Simonneau G, Torbicki A, Dorfmueller P, et al. The pathophysiology of chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension. *Eur Respir Rev* 2017;**26**:160112, <https://doi.org/10.1183/16000617.0112-2016>.
- Páez Carpio A, Vollmer I, Zarco FX, et al. Imaging of chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension before, during and after balloon pulmonary angioplasty. *Diagn Interv Imaging* 2024;**105**:215–26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.diii.2024.02.005>.
- Lang IM, Dorfmueller P, Vonk Noordegraaf AV, et al. The pathobiology of chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension. *Ann Am Thorac Soc* 2016;**13**:S215–21. <https://doi.org/10.1513/AnnalsATS.201509-620AS>.
- Tunari N, Gibbs SJR, Win Z, et al. Ventilation perfusion scintigraphy is more sensitive than multidetector CTPA in detecting chronic thromboembolic pulmonary disease as a treatable cause of pulmonary

- hypertension. *J Nucl Med* 2007;**48**:680–8. <https://doi.org/10.2967/jnumed.106.039438>.
9. Wang M, Wu D, Ma R, et al. Comparison of V/Q SPECT and CT angiography for the diagnosis of chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension. *Radiology* 2020;**296**:420–9. <https://doi.org/10.1148/radiol.2020192181>.
 10. Remy Jardin M, Ryerson CJ, Schiebler ML, et al. Imaging of pulmonary hypertension in adults: a position paper from the fleischner society. *Radiology* 2021;**298**:531–49. <https://doi.org/10.1148/radiol.2020203108>.
 11. Swift AJ, Rajaram S. CT pulmonary angiography in chronic thromboembolic disease: where do we stand? *Radiology* 2020;**296**:430–1. <https://doi.org/10.1148/radiol.2020201344>.
 12. Dournes G, Verdier D, Montaudon M, et al. Dual energy CT perfusion and angiography in chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension: diagnostic accuracy and concordance with radionuclide scintigraphy. *Eur Radiol* 2014;**24**:42–51. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00330-013-2975-y>.
 13. Páez Carpio A, Gómez FM, Maschke S, et al. Cone beam CT pulmonary angiography in balloon pulmonary angioplasty for chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension: a review of technical parameters and benefits. *Eur J Radiol* 2025;**186**:112047. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejrad.2025.112047>.
 14. Sugiyama M, Fukuda T, Sanda Y, et al. Organized thrombus in pulmonary arteries in patients with chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension: imaging with cone beam computed tomography. *Jpn J Radiol* 2014;**32**:375–82. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11604-014-0319-8>.
 15. Maschke SK, Werncke T, Dewald CLA, et al. Depiction of mosaic perfusion in chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension on C arm computed tomography compared to computed tomography pulmonary angiogram. *Sci Rep* 2021;**11**:20042. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-99658-2>.
 16. Hinrichs JB, Von Falck C, Hoepfer MM, et al. Pulmonary artery imaging in patients with chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension: Comparison of cone beam CT and 64 row multidetector CT. *J Vasc Interv Radiol* 2016;**27**:361–368.e2. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvir.2015.11.046>.
 17. Nakazawa T, Watanabe Y, Hori Y, et al. Lung perfused blood volume images with dual energy computed tomography for chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension: correlation to scintigraphy with single photon emission computed tomography. *J Comput Assist Tomogr* 2011;**35**. <https://doi.org/10.1097/RCT.0b013e318224e227>.
 18. Ende Verhaar YM, Meijboom LJM, Kroft LJM, et al. Usefulness of standard computed tomography pulmonary angiography performed for acute pulmonary embolism for identification of chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension: results of the InShape III study. *J Heart Lung Transplant* 2019;**38**:731–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.healun.2019.03.003>.
 19. Reichelt A, Hoepfer MM, Galanski M, et al. Chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension: evaluation with 64 detector row CT versus digital subtraction angiography. *Eur J Radiol* 2009;**71**:49–54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejrad.2008.03.016>.
 20. Saeedan MB, Bullen J, Heresi GA, et al. Morphologic and functional dual energy CT parameters in patients with chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension and chronic thromboembolic disease. *AJR Am J Roentgenol* 2020;**215**:1335–41. <https://doi.org/10.2214/AJR.19.22743>.
 21. Meinel F, Graef A, Thierfelder K, et al. Automated quantification of pulmonary perfused blood volume by dual energy CTPA in chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension. *Fortschr Röntgenstr* 2013;**186**:151–6. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0033-1350412>.
 22. Takagi H, Ota H, Sugimura K, et al. Dual energy CT to estimate clinical severity of chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension: Comparison with invasive right heart catheterization. *Eur J Radiol* 2016;**85**:1574–80. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejrad.2016.06.010>.
 23. Koike H, Sueyoshi E, Sakamoto I, et al. Comparative clinical and predictive value of lung perfusion blood volume CT, lung perfusion SPECT and catheter pulmonary angiography images in patients with chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension before and after balloon pulmonary angioplasty. *Eur Radiol* 2018;**28**:5091–9. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00330-018-5501-4>.
 24. Koike H, Sueyoshi E, Sakamoto I, et al. Correlation between lung perfusion blood volume and SPECT images in patients with chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension by balloon pulmonary angioplasty. *Clin Imaging* 2018;**49**:80–6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clinimag.2017.11.001>.
 25. Abozeed M, Conic S, Bullen J, et al. Dual energy CT based scoring in chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension and correlation with clinical and hemodynamic parameters: a retrospective cross sectional study. *Cardiovasc Diagn Ther* 2022;**12**:305–13. <https://doi.org/10.21037/cdt-21-686>.
 26. Renapurkar RD, Bolen MA, Shrikanthan S, et al. Comparative assessment of qualitative and quantitative perfusion with dual energy CT and planar and SPECT CT V/V scanning in patients with chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension. *Cardiovasc Diagn Ther* 2018;**8**:414–22. <https://doi.org/10.21037/cdt.2018.05.07>.
 27. Schüßler A, Richter M, Tello K, et al. Evaluation of diagnostic accuracy and radiation exposure of dual energy computed tomography in the course of chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension. *RöFo* 2021;**193**:1318–26. <https://doi.org/10.1055/a-1502-7541>.
 28. Páez Carpio A, Zarco FX, Serrano E, et al. Cone beam CT pulmonary angiography in balloon pulmonary angioplasty for chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension during the program initiation period. *Clin Radiol* 2025;**84**:106847. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crad.2025.106847>.